

DEVELOPMENT CONDITIONS AND MODERN TRENDS OF BUSINESS TOURISM WORLDWIDE

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Abstract. *This article examines the need for stability in service areas, strengthening the health care system in hotels, environmental pollution, the use of ecologically clean energy, food hygiene, and the integration of service and leisure issues.*

Keywords: *Tourism, service, corporate travelers, leisure tourism, destination, business.*

УСЛОВИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ И СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ ДЕЛОВОГО ТУРИЗМА В МИРЕ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются необходимость стабильности в сфере обслуживания, усиление системы здравоохранения в гостиницах, загрязнение окружающей среды, использование экологически чистой энергии, гигиена питания, интеграция вопросов обслуживания и досуга.*

Ключевые слова: *Туризм, сервис, корпоративные путешественники, рекреационный туризм, направление, бизнес.*

INTRODUCTION

2019 was one of the most successful years for the development of tourism worldwide. Visits to other countries around the world reached 1,481 million and the gross income was 1,460 billion US dollars.

The distribution of inbound tourism by purpose in 2019 was as follows: leisure, entertainment and recreation tourism - 55%, health recovery, visiting relatives and friends, etc. - 28%, business and professional purposes - 11%, unspecified purpose - 6%.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In 2020, international tourism was hit hard by the Covid-19 pandemic, with an unprecedented drop in arrivals. According to UNNVTO, the number of international visits in 2020 fell by one billion, or 74 percent, compared to 2019 due to the coronavirus pandemic and widespread travel restrictions. Tourism export earnings fell by \$1.3 trillion, 11 times more than during the 2009 global economic crisis. Between 100 and 120 million tourism jobs are at risk, most of them in small and medium-sized businesses.

In 2021, the growth rate of global tourism was 4%: the number of overnight stays by international tourists increased by 15 million compared to 2020, but remained at 72% compared to 2019. The five months of 2022 saw a sharp increase in international tourism, with overnight stays up 221% compared to the same period in 2021, with nearly 250 million international visits recorded worldwide.

RESULTS

Today's trends in world tourism and expert assessments show that business tourism is becoming one of the main factors in the recovery of the industry in the new conditions. World Travel & Tourism Council (WTTC) forecasts that in 2022, the number of business trips is expected to increase by 41%, and over the next 10 years, the growth rate of this type of visits will be 5.5% per year on average.

Many new entrants are entering this market. Corporate travelers are more interested in India and Indonesia. according to the report, the growth rate of these markets in 2019 was equal to 11.3% and 8.7%, and by the end of 2022, India may enter the top five of the business travel market. Today, these five include the United States (\$354.31 billion), the European Union (\$240.82 billion), China (\$179.44 billion), Japan (\$79.26 billion) and Great Britain (\$68. \$31 billion).

Recovery of business tourism after the pandemic and predicting its prospects are in the focus of many experts.

The following are the main factors and trends affecting business tourism:¹

- The most anticipated innovation in business tourism today is the younger generation of travelers. According to analysts, up to 40% of employees sent on business trips are under 30 years old.² Along with middle-aged employees, they make up the bulk of corporate travelers.

- Integration of business with leisure. According to 2019 data, 90% of business travelers extended their business trip to use their free time. And companies can ensure adequate labor productivity through telecommuting and job scheduling. Recent studies show that travelers try to combine business trips with work vacations and prefer to travel with family members;

- Increasing focus on smaller accommodations than traditional hotels. 74% of middle-aged travelers chose small hotels;

- Independent booking of hotels and tickets, that is, the choice of means of accommodation and travel by the employee himself. 68% of employees like to use different reservation systems (Expedia Group, 2021);

- Companies are also more liberal with employees' means of travel choices. Employee performance monitoring programs are becoming more remote and situational (TripActions, 2019);

- Development of technologies for organizing service trips. Mobile technologies are widely used in such matters as booking, customs clearance, changing routes, keeping in touch. At the same time, the penetration of artificial intelligence technologies in the management of services (Wishup, 2019), Siri, Cortana Google Now software assistants, the need to develop routes is increasing. Based on this, the increasing importance of blockchain technologies in data protection is also gaining great importance;

- Flexibility of companies and tourism business representatives. According to Robinson's research, 72% of employees say flexibility is the key to business travel.

DISCUSSION

The following characteristics of American business tourism in the post-pandemic situation can be observed:

Require stability in service areas. In this case, travelers understand sustainability as strengthening the health care system in hotels, non-polluting the environment, using ecologically clean energy, food hygiene, safety of relationships, etc. Companies also agree to increase service prices in accordance with these requirements;

The new content of the service trip. Business travelers often seek to combine service and leisure. For this purpose, it is necessary to adjust the venues of the events accordingly, and to

¹<https://financesonline.com/business-travel-trends/>

²<https://connectteam.com/generation-z-in-the-workplace/2020>

liberalize them a bit. Offers are being developed so that the leisure schedule of corporate travelers does not interfere with their work duties. Long-term business travel is one of today's most attractive brands;

Switch to a multi-option booking process. Changing local conditions on the spot leaves travelers with little time, so bookings need to be quick, flexible and flexible.

CONCLUSION

The fact that service trips are tied to local conditions does not guarantee that all participants will be in the same conditions. A lockdown or announcement of additional security measures will make it difficult for everyone to participate in person. In this situation, it is expected that hybrid meetings, that is, the provision of conference rooms in hotels with the Internet and virtual communication tools, will be a common occurrence.

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